

Uppsala universitet

This form has been closed, and can therefore not be answered.

Towards a Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science: Co-creation with the Global community 2024/05

Available 2024-05-22 – 2025-01-15
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Thank you for your interest in being part of this co-creative process by taking our survey: Towards a Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science.

This survey is part of the BioEcoOcean project: Co-Creating Transformative Pathways to Biological and Ecosystem Ocean Observations funded by Horizon Europe (Grant Agreement Number: 101136748).

We are co-creating a Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science with a focus on biology and ecosystems in the ocean. The vision for the Blueprint is to create a question-based support tool to enable and encourage collaboration to increase our understanding of the ocean and especially its marine life. The Blueprint aims to include all aspects of ocean observing; from reviewing, planning, data collection, data management, analysis, modelling, data products to policy application and beyond.

This survey takes about 8-10 minutes and it is the very first step in the Blueprint development. Your input is therefore very important. The Blueprint development process will be accessible on www.BioEcoOcean.org. The ready product will be launched as a resource platform in autumn 2027.

Yours sincerely,
Associate Professor Lina Mtwana Nordlund & Dr. Artur Palacz

And the rest of the BioEcoOcean consortium:
Uppsala University (UU), Institut Oceanologii Polskiej Akademii Nauk (IO PAN), United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS), European Global Ocean Observing System (EUROGOOS), Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU), University of Pisa (UINPI), Centro Interdisciplinar de Investigacao Marinha E Ambiental (CIIMAR), Mercator Ocean International (MOI), Atlantic International Research Centre (Air Center) and Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON).

Ethics and privacy statement

It is possible to respond to the survey anonymously, but in addition to your opinions, we would like to collect your name and email address to be able to contact you for follow-up (if needed), and invite you to participate in this co-creative process again.

We process and securely store your personal data as long as it is necessary to ensure the quality of the research. We respect your trust and protect your privacy, and therefore will never sell or share this data with any third parties. The outcome of this survey will be published and made openly available. All data will be analysed without any personal information, which means that it will not be possible to identify any individual in the output.

By filling out this survey form you agree that we will process your data in line with our Privacy Policy (<https://www.uu.se/en/about-uu/data-protection-policy>).

1. Do you agree to participate in this study? - Required

Yes

2. Your name (optional)

3. Your email address (optional)

4. Which category(-ies) best describes you and/or your activities:

Student **Scientist** **Education** **Policy and decision-making** **Management** **NGO** **Governmental Agency** **Intergovernmental Agency** **Traditional, Indigenous or Marine-Dependent Communities** **Private Sector** **Other****5. How many years of professional experience (work experience) do you have?** **0-3 years** **4-8 years** **9-15 years** **16+ years****6. In which country are you based for work / studies?**

7. Which “domain/-s” do you have most professional experience of? **Coast (Land affected by the sea)** **Coastal zone (coastline and seaward)** **Offshore (surface ocean)** **Offshore (deep ocean)** **Other****8. Which Ocean basin(s) do you have the most professional experience with? Select all that apply.** **Arctic Ocean** **North Pacific Ocean** **Northeast Pacific Ocean off the coasts of North America** **Northwest Pacific Ocean off Far Eastern Asia** **Greenland Sea** **Norwegian Sea** **Baltic Sea** **Northwestern Atlantic Ocean off North America** **Northeastern Atlantic Ocean off Europe**

North Atlantic Ocean **Labrador Sea** **Black Sea** **Caspian Sea** **Western Indian Ocean** **Eastern Indian Ocean** **Southeast Atlantic Ocean off Africa** **Southwest Atlantic Ocean off South America** **Southeast Atlantic Ocean** **Southwest Atlantic Ocean** **Southeast Pacific Ocean off South America** **Southwest Pacific Ocean around Oceania** **Southern Ocean** **Other (please specify)**

9. Which category(-ies) best describes your professional activities. Select all that apply.

 Review (e.g. reviewing the goals of ocean observing, investigate state-of-the-art solutions, identifying best practices) **Planning (e.g. plan and decide the context and set the limits for the process, what, how and when to do it, goals of the process, other actors involved)**

Data collection (e.g. gathering or collecting data such as ecological surveys, interviews, data mining)

Data management (e.g. ingesting, storing, organizing and maintaining the collected data, reporting, sharing, publishing open access data)

Analysis and modelling (e.g. data analysis and model development, statistics, interpretations)

Data Products (e.g. development and delivery of data synthesis and modelling products such as maps, indicators, early warning systems, forecasts and future scenarios of change)

Policy application (e.g. integration of data and knowledge into policy and science-based decision making, use of data products, identification of policy needs)

Evaluation (e.g. evaluation of produced data and information, policy needs, and the ocean observing process)

Other (please specify)

Developing the Blueprint with focus on marine life

In this section, we provide five sets of statements.

We would like to know to what extent you agree with these statements.

Answers like 'Do not know' are as valuable as any other response.

We define DATA as biological and ecosystem (BioEco) ocean observations along with other variables/measurements.

10. SET 1 (of 5). From your point of view to what extent do you agree with the following statements?

a. Global scientific assessments are useful to non-scientific audiences

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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b. Social, cultural and economic information is important for understanding changes of marine life

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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c. The diverse nature of the data collected on local level makes it impossible to use on larger scales

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

<input type="radio"/>					
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d. Data is not made openly available

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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e. We know what data is needed for good and accurate data products

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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f. Citizen science programs collecting data on marine life contributes to our knowledge

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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g. Feedback from data users is considered when designing the ocean observing system

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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11. SET 2 (of 5). From your point of view to what extent do you agree with the following statements?

a. Locally collected data is not comparable with data from other areas

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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b. We have a good understanding of marine life

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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c. There are good solutions to make data openly available

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

<input type="radio"/>					
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d. It is easy to make BioEco data integrated and comparable to other areas

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

<input type="radio"/>					
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e. Technology and infrastructure are commonly used to their full advantage

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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f. Data and model products for marine life (e.g. indicators, maps, forecasts) are accurate

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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g. Data sharing has no drawbacks

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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12. SET 3 (of 5). From your point of view to what extent do you agree with the following statements?**a. We are bridging national priorities towards global needs**

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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b. Locally collected data does not have high enough quality for larger assessments

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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c. There are solutions to make data useful at a global level

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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d. Data collected today are appropriate for the data and model products needed

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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e. There is a need for improved understanding of marine life in the ocean

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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f. Ocean data services are easy to use (e.g. national space agency services, data repositories)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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g. There is good capacity to forecast the status and trends of BioEco processes

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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13. SET 4 (of 5). From your point of view to what extent do you agree with the following statements?**a. There is poor coordination when it comes to data collection**

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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b. We have enough information on marine life and its changes to make informed science-based decisions

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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c. There is high awareness of how to make data available to others

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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d. There is high awareness of uncertainty (accuracy issues) associated with indicators and predictions

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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e. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reuseable (FAIR) data should be the norm

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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f. Indigenous and traditional ecological knowledge is integrated in the ocean observing system

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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g. There are useful and robust ocean information service providers

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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14. SET 5 (of 5). From your point of view to what extent do you agree with the following statements?

a. Verification of data products are common (checking how accurate they are)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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b. Global assessments of marine life are important

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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c. Feedback from policy makers is considered when designing the ocean observing system

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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d. Data and model products are fit-for purpose (i.e. the data products are useful and meet the needs)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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e. There is good coordination among stakeholders when it comes to data collection

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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f. Associated metadata is often insufficient or missing (e.g. dates, GPS coordinates, methods, quality flags)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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g. It is easy to find ocean-related data needed for different purposes

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree Do not know

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15. Are you working with any of the following threats to marine life? Select all that apply. **Plastics and ocean debris** **Fishing and fishing gear** **Shipping and transport**

Offshore drilling **Climate change** **Deep-sea mining** **Invasive species / disease** **Coastal development** **Eutrophication** **Other (please specify)**

16. How familiar are you with the Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), incl. specification sheets, data schema standards etc.?

Never heard of Vaguely familiar To some extent Familiar Very familiar Do not know

<input type="radio"/>					
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17. Are you aware of any good examples of collaborations among ocean observers, service providers and users of ocean information connected to marine life, that you would like to share with us?

18. Is there anything else you would like to share with us?

19. If you would like to be acknowledged for your contribution, please add your name, as you would like it to appear in the acknowledgement.